

ENPOWER
POWER IN OUR HANDS

D6.2 | ENPOWER Pilots' execution documentation and consumers' engagement – pre-pilot phase

WATT-IS

January 2025

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Energy Activated Citizens and Data-Driven Energy-Secure Communities for a Consumer-Centric Energy System

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Preface

ENPOWER designs, develops, and demonstrates SSH-driven methodologies, interactive and closed-loop tools, and data-driven services for energy-activated citizens and energy-secure cross-sector communities towards a citizen-centric energy system. By combining leading-edge ICTs with social/behavioural dimensions and with sharing economy and value stacking business models the project aims to deploy: 1) a Social Science Framework for energy citizens activation and innovative multidimensional incentives for citizens' participation in energy markets; 2) AI-based consumers clustering and segmentation algorithms; 3) interactive tools and facilitation services for energy community planning; 4) Energy Data Space adaptation to support community-level data-driven activation and interoperable automated privacy and sovereignty-preserving Demand Response (DR); 5) (Peer-to-Peer) P2P DLT/Blockchain digital marketplace for tokenized energy and non-energy assets reciprocal compensation; 6) data-driven services and apps for energy efficiency and activation performance management; 7) ICT services and Digital Twins for community-level energy optimisation and aggregated flexibility management to trade off local self-consumption against grid service provisioning, while boosting a beyond-energy community social welfare; 8) Edge monitoring hubs for automated DR; 9) Business Sandbox for novel sharing economy and social innovation-based business models; 10) methodologies for evaluating different energy community setups, upscaling and replication. ENPOWER framework will be validated along 4 Front Runners energy communities' pilots and further replicated in 2 Early Adopters, covering different levels of maturity of communities, to demonstrate increased RES local self-consumption and consumers participation to the energy markets, while nurturing increased local security of supply. ENPOWER Leadership Programme and blueprints will support EU-wide replication and advice regulatory bodies on communities-friendly enabling frameworks.

Who we are.

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4	Fundación CARTIF (CARTIF Technology Center)	CARTIF	ES	
5	COMSENSUS D.O.O.	COMS	SL	
6	European Dynamics Luxembourg SA	ED	LU	
7	Audencia Business School	AUDENCIA	FR	
8	Regulatory Assistance Project	RAP	BE	Regulatory assistance
9	ICLEI Europasekretariat GmbH	ICLEI	DE	Policy & capacity
10	University of Basel(<i>associated partner</i>)	UNIBAS	CH	Social framework
11	Blueprint Energy Solutions GMBH	BLUEPRINT	AT	Pilot 1 - Austria (Front runners)
12	OurPower Energiegenossenschaft SCE	OurPower	AT	
13	Cooperativa de Desenvolvimento Sustentável, CRL	COOPERNICO	PT	Pilot 2 - Portugal (Front runners)
14	WATT-IS SA	WATT-IS	PT	
15	Cooperativa Eléctrica do Vale D'Este CRL	CEVE	PT	
16	EnC of Chalki'Chalkion'	ChalkiON	GR	Pilot 3 - Greece (Front runners)
17	Hellenic Association for Energy Economics	HAEE	GR	
18	Green Energy Aggregator Services SA	GEARS	GR	
19	Parity Platform P.C.	PARITY	GR	
20	Electric Power Research Institute Europe DAC	EEU	IE	Pilot 4 - Ireland (Front runners)
21	University College Cork (MaREI Centre for Energy, Climate and Marine, Environmental Research Institute)	UCC	IE	
22	DC Six Technologies Limited	DCSix	IE	
23	MOL TEIC - Dingle Hub	DINGLE HUB	IE	
24	ESB Innovation ROI Limited	ESB	IE	
25	Békéscsaba Energia ESCO Kft.	BCS	HU	Pilot 5 - Hungary (Early adopters)
26	Enasco Cleantech Alliance LLC.	ENASCO	HU	
27	Montajes Eléctricos Cuerva SL	CUERVA	ES	Pilot 6 - Spain (Early adopters)
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Executive Summary

Deliverable D6.2 – “ENPOWER Pilots’ execution documentation and consumers’ engagement – pre-pilot phase” describes the development status of the pilots involved in ENPOWER at the pre-pilot phase, so at a stage where the pilots have not been launched yet. This document gives a detailed overview of any deviations from the proposed development of the pilots and their actual status before being launched. This document follows D6.1, where the development roadmap and evaluation methodology of the proposed technologies had been described.

Participant engagement is one of the most defining points in the successful implementation of the pilots, as each pilot follows a specific strategy to engage the proposed participants in ENPOWER. At this pre-pilot stage, the engagement strategies have been implemented, and the number of participants should be confirmed for each pilot, and such update is given in this document, justifying any possible deviation from the initially proposed engaged participants.

Following the evaluation methodology defined in D6.1, crucial to quantify the goals of the project, this document describes the progress on the defined key performance indicators (KPIs), giving an update on any possible changes in the way those KPIs will be measured or if, by some reason, they can no longer be measured. Hence, at a pre-pilot phase, the different data sources have been identified, tested and determined whether this implementation is feasible or if any setback occurred. The different data sources in each pilot depend on a specific technology and data transfer process that have been previously characterised so, at this point of development, an evaluation has been done on the availability and implementation of those technologies and if any alternative technology should be considered.

Finally, this document provides an update on the general development of each pilot, updating the Gantt chart provided in D6.1, thus serving as a significant tool to manage ENPOWER progress.

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List of acronyms

BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
CEC	Citizen energy community
CRP	Citizen Renewable Platform
DSO	Distribution system operator
EnC	Energy community
EV	Electric vehicle
ICT	Information and communication technology
KPI	Key performance indicator
PV	Photovoltaic
REC	Renewable energy community
SEC	Sustainable Energy Community
SM	Sub Meter
SSH	Social sciences and humanities
TBD	To be discussed
TE	Technological enabler
WP	Work package

1 Introduction

1.1 About this document

This document has been developed to provide an update on each pilot implementation at a pre-pilot stage, so before being effectively deployed.

This deliverable focuses on the status on participant engagement, data source availability, KPI evaluation and the status on the technology enablers. It also provides a general update of the development timeline of each pilot.

1.2 Relationships and Connections with ENPOWER WPs

The information collected in this document comes from an initial analysis of the context and pilots, and from HLUC described in D2.1. In subsequent deliverables, this information will be implemented or slightly modified as needed.

This document has been developed with the participation of the project partners, TEs leaders and pilots' leaders under the scope of task 6.7. The pilot sites leaders from the Early Adopters (Hungary and Spain) were involved with a minimum effort as they do not have human resources allocated to this task. This document was developed with the efforts undertaken in WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5 and with the outputs from deliverable 6.1.

- The engagement initiatives were undertaken in WP2, which were fundamental to attract participants into the project. These initiatives have been described in D6.1 and these engagement results are described in this document.
- The KPIs were the result of the efforts in WP3, especially T3.1. This document provides an update to these KPIs, namely if any KPI could already started to be quantified (such as energy saving or number of engaged users)
- The technology that has been developed in WP4 and WP5 is now characterized in this pre-pilot stage, referring to the status and any possible change from the projected developments.

This document gives an update of the development status of the development of the pilots, referring to the developed technologies, data transfer processes, engagement of participants and timeline. Changes from the projected developments are discussed as well, thus outlining the status in the pre-pilot phase.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

This document is structured as follows:

- Section 3 gives an update on the engagement activities undertaken in the project. Each pilot has carried out specific engagement activities such as holding workshops or other communication activities, providing the conclusions and outcomes of each initiative. A user satisfaction survey is also described which will be implemented in future engagement initiatives.
- Sections 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9 describe the updates in each pilot, respectively Austria, Portugal, Greece, Ireland, Hungary and Spain. Each of these sections is divided into three parts, describing the pilot status, the progress on the impact analysis (referring to the KPIs and available technology) and the update on the respective implementation plan.
- Section 10 concludes this document.

2 Engagement updates

This section describes the engagement activities that were undertaken by the pilots, assessing the response from participants and the engaged participants in the project. The engagement activities ranged from holding workshops, demonstrations or training sessions, focusing on various topics, namely the tools that will be implemented in each pilot or on other topics related to energy communities (EnC) or on sustainability, thus focusing in sensitizing the participants to the ENPOWER objectives.

2.1 Engagement activities and workshops in the pilot sites

The following table summarizes the various engagement initiatives that have been undertaken.

Table 1: Promotion initiatives from all pilots.

Type of workshop (Awareness, training programmes, etc)	Location/ Pilot	Month	Tool to be promoted	Additional means of promotion (presentation, brochure etc)
Deliberative Workshop	Ireland	M5	Citizen Renewable Platform	Opportunities in Data sharing; Brainstorming; Presentation CRP; Testimonial
Deliberative Workshop	Ireland	M7	Citizen Renewable Platform	Defining 'Energy Data Sharing'; Presentation Scenarios; Demonstration CRP; Development of recommendations
Solar PV demonstration day	Ireland	M10	Citizen Renewable Platform	presentation, hands-on training
Deliberative Workshop	Austrian	M10	OurPower Market Place	Opportunities in Data sharing; Brainstorming; Testimonial; Expert presentation
Deliberative Workshop	Austrian	M11	OurPower Market Place	Defining 'Energy Data Sharing'; Presentation Scenarios; Development of recommendations
Deliberative Workshop	Portugal	M14	CARTIF. WATT-IS. INESC TEC	Story collection, lessons learned,

				Solution presentation	
Energy Master Plan Launch	Ireland		M14	Citizen Renewable Platform	Presentation, Registration support
Solar PV demonstration day	Ireland		M15	Citizen Renewable Platform	Presentation, Registration support
Energy Efficiency workshop	Ireland		M15	Citizen Renewable Platform	Presentation, Registration support
Awareness raising & training workshop	Chalki Island (Greece)		M20-M21	Technical Enablers - Demand response tool for households and vehicles	presentation, hands-on training (?)
Awareness raising & training workshop & feedback from the summer period	Chalki Island (Greece)		M26-M27	Technical Enablers - Demand response tool for households and vehicles	TBD

More specifically, the following activities were conducted in the pilots:

Austrian Pilot

In August 2024, the OurPower platform was presented to some of the members of the energy community in Poysdorf. The goal of the workshop was to present the functionalities of the platform and engage the members to it. More details on the results of the workshop can be found in D2.5 Enabling conditions for consumer-centric energy system.

Portuguese Pilot

The workshop organised in the Portuguese pilot comprised of two sessions focusing on energy communities in Portugal. The first session explored the context of these communities by allowing community leaders to share their stories and motivations. The second session identified barriers to the growth of energy communities and featured presentations from CARTIF and its community engagement platform, the WATT-IS community platform, as well as insights from INESC TEC regarding algorithms and energy management. The workshop was organised also as part of Task 5.1 activities and a final presentation of the workshop’s results is among the plans of the pilot.

The feedback received from the workshop regarding the CARTIF’s tool, (the community engagement platform) highlighted that it is a tool designed for the energy community managers (community champions) and it should also address energy poverty, which is crucial for the community and for its effective management. The potential user segments include permanent residents, secondary residence owners, and homeowners who do not consume energy. Finally, the tool should provide disaggregated data for these specific segments.

Greek Pilot

Regarding the Greek Pilot, the planning of the two workshops on the island of Chalki is currently underway. These workshops designed to be of technical and instructional character, serving as tutorials for the local residents. Coordinating between HAEE and Chalki energy community has

been established to facilitate these events, which are scheduled for the summer of 2025. The primary goal of these activities is to increase community engagement, inform the residents about the ENPOWER project and its services, and provide training to stakeholders on how to use the available tools.

Irish Pilot

On October 23, 2024, the Energy Master Plan (EMP) was launched at An Díseart in Dingle, Co. Kerry, Ireland, bringing together local and regional leaders to discuss energy transition within the tourism and hospitality sector. The event featured presentations from key organizations such as DCSix, Dingle Hub, Fáilte Ireland, and University College Cork (UCC), with the Cathaoirleach emphasizing the importance of community participation in the energy transition to support the climate action plan. Fáilte Ireland highlighted the cost-saving benefits of participating in the EMP and signing up for the Citizen Renewable Platform (CRP), a key discussion point amidst rising operational costs in the tourism sector.

The event drew a diverse audience, predominantly women, and fostered open dialogue and engagement. While many attendees expressed interest in the EMP and CRP, older women voiced concerns about long-term investment viability, given their uncertainty about business continuity. Although flyers with QR codes were widely distributed, they saw limited immediate use, with many preferring to explore the platform later, often with assistance. Despite these challenges, the event successfully raised awareness and encouraged collaboration toward sustainable energy solutions in the community.

2.2 Workshops feedback and insights

To receive feedback and insights into the tools presented in the workshops organised at the pilot sites, we proposed and developed a User Satisfaction Survey to evaluate the satisfaction of participants involved in the engagement and training activities. This survey can be used as a primary method for collecting feedback as it allows for the structured gathering of responses.

The feedback questionnaire is a customisable template that can be adapted to meet the unique needs of each pilot case, depending on the type of workshop conducted. This survey is presented in the Annex to this document.

Beyond this survey, the organisers of the workshops and the training sessions may choose to adopt alternative methods depending on the background of the energy communities and the specific characteristics of the workshop. For instance, informal discussions or group discussions can foster an interactive environment, encouraging participants to share their opinions more freely.

3 Pilot 1 -Austria

3.1 Pilot status

The Austrian pilot has been split into two pilot communities: Energiegemeinschaft (Renewable Energy Community) Spörbichl-Dreißgen (REC SD), with an operating region in Mühlviertel, Upper Austria, and Energiegemeinschaft Poysdorf (REC POY), with an operating region in Weinviertel, Lower Austria.

REC SD: A regional renewable energy community with a community-financed wind farm. During the start-up phase of the energy community, there were some major challenges with the energy service provider of the windfarm, as the participation of windfarms in energy communities is difficult and needs special support. Despite these challenges, the **energy cooperative REGIOS** with community-financed power plants in the region of the REC Spörbichl-Dreißgen was founded in November 2024. The REC Spörbichl-Dreißgen and its wind farm will also be part of this cooperative.

REC POY In June 2024, the Regional Renewable Energy Community Poysdorf started and joined the ENPOWER project. In August 2024, a kick-off event took place in Poysdorf with over 100 participants. On 13 December 2024, another onboarding event for new Energy Community participants took place. The energy community has been in regular operation since September 2024 and the framework conditions for further growth are in place.

3.1.1 Progress on pilot engagement

In this we characterize the participants that will effectively participate in the pilot and compare with what we were planning.

REC SD: The official launch of REC Spörbichl-Dreißgen will take place once the organisational difficulties with the energy service providers have been resolved. That's why, at this stage, the Renewable Energy Community only consists of one 1.3 MW wind farm and one company as a consumer, instead of the 25 consumers/prosumers originally planned.

REC POY: Currently the Energy Community consists of 5 producers with 700 kWp of photovoltaic (rooftop) production and 39 consumers. The goal for the next six months is to expand the Energy Community to at least 100 participating households and businesses.

3.1.2 Progress on infrastructure development and implementation

The table below describes the equipment that will be installed in the pilot's demonstration activities and their status of development. This table refers to the development from the respective table related to the pilot infrastructure in D6.1.

Table 2: Equipment characterization in the Austrian pilot.

Equipment						
Equipment	Expected number of units	Confirmed number of units	Expected number of new units	Confirmed number of new units	Status	Expected date
Windfarm REGIOS (REC SD)	1	1	0	0	Installed and operating (1.3 MW)	Start of REC during

					REGIOS is operating REC SD is not yet operating	next six months
Photovoltaic rooftop REGIOS (REC SD)	5	5	tbd	tbd	Installed and operating (1.3 MW) REGIOS is operating REC SD is not yet operating	Start of REC during next six months
Photovoltaic rooftop (REC POY)	5	5	0	0	Installed and operating (700 kWp) REC POY is operating	

3.1.3 Progress on data sources availability

The table below shows the development status of all the data sources that will be utilised for the pilot's demonstration activities, which have been referenced in D6.1.

Table 3 – Data collection status for the Austrian pilot.

Partner Data Collection	
DSO "Smart Meter"	
Current implementation status	Smart meters are installed at all participating consumption points. The electrical consumption or generation per meter point as 1/4h-values is continuously provided via DSO.
Expected availability date	-

3.2 Impact analysis

3.2.1 Progress on the Key Performance Indicators

This section provides an update in the KPIs, revising the actual quantification of each KPI in the pre-pilot phase. Hence, should KPIs have started to be monitored, such as the number of engaged users or shared energy in the EnC, these values are updated.

Table 4 – Status of the key performance indexes for the Austrian pilot.

	KPI	Name	Baseline	Comments
Social	KPI1-SO1	N° of energy communities created and/or upgraded with active members	0	
	KPI1-SO2	N° of energy citizens engaged	0	
	KPI1-SO4	Rate of engaged citizens that become activated (e.g. at the	0%	

		individual level or as energy community members)		
	KPI2-SO1	% of energy bill reduction for energy community members	0%	
	KPI2-SO3	% kWh supplied within the RECs / CECs	-	Baseline for this KPI will be prepared later
	KPI3-SO1	Increased energy data sharing by active consumers	0	
	KPI4-SO1	% of consumers with sustainable (for more than 6 months) using DR automated solutions	0	
	KPI5-SO1	Carbon emissions reduction (environmental benefit) measured at piloted local community levels of community engagement and the adoption of the new services	0	
Technological	KPI3-ET1	Share of new market roles designed, enabled and validated along the pilots	0%	
	KPI3-ET2	New market participants as individual prosumers/consumers or through intermediaries (e.g. energy communities, aggregators)	0	
	KPI5-ET2	Share of increased aggregated flexibility the adoption of the new services	0%	

3.2.2 Technology enablers evaluation in the pre-pilot phase

This section summarizes the different technology enablers (TEs) that will be deployed in this pilot, following what has been previously described in D2.1. In the case of this pilot, no changes have been identified, so the TEs to implement remain the ones described in the table below.

Furthermore, TEs 14 “Nudging Apps for near real time closed loop consumers activation” and 16 “P2P digital tools and platforms for consumer activation / social engagement” have not yet been demonstrated or implemented in the Austrian pilot communities. There was just a first presentation of possible mock-ups for the TEs in August 2024.

Table 5 - TEs description in the Austrian pilot.

TE-#	TE Description	Partner
TE-1	Interactive decision support tool for EnC planning	CARTIF, INESC TEC
TE-4	Energy Data Space compliant tools for sovereign data management, semantic interoperability and exploitation	ED, DST
TE-5	DLT/Blockchain/smart contracts multi-purpose marketplace for increased Trust & Sovereignty and for P2P tokenised assets sharing and compensation	DST
TE-6	Digital Twins for consumer activation	INESC TEC, DST

4 Pilot 2 – Portugal

4.1 Pilot status

The following sections describe the status of the pilot technologies to implement in the pre-phase stage of the pilot. For the Portuguese pilot, two pilots were envisioned, one where CEVE is the coordinator and another where Coopérnico is the coordinator. Being split in two, the Portuguese pilot has two different goals.

- On one hand, CEVE will manage an EnC with up to 33 participants where an EnC management platform will be implemented (WIS4Communities) with a user engagement platform (WIS4Households – TE-13) that will help end users to be more efficient and, overall, maximizing the benefit of the EnC. Finally, if technically possible, demand response will also be implemented in up to 10 houses.
- On the other hand, Coopérnico, being a national-wide energy cooperative, has targeted 100 end users to participate in the pilot. As these participants will have various locations, a physical EnC will not be developed but rather the different strategies will be tested with the deployment of TE-13 – WIS4Households, where end users will have tailored feedback on their energy consumption profiles, demand response will be installed if technically possible in up to 10 houses and the EnC benefits will be simulated in a selection of end users.

Various integration approaches have been explored for each pilot. During the pre-pilot phase, an existing data integration setup between Watt-IS (the technology provider) and CEVE (the pilot provider and EnC manager) was utilized. This setup included specific endpoints, allowing Watt-IS to access data such as smart meter consumption information. Following this, the focus shifted to integrating data into WIS4Households, with the process expected to conclude by April 2025.

For Coopérnico’s pilot, there was no prior data integration in place, necessitating the creation of a data transfer mechanism via an SFTP process. This process concerned smart meter data and was successfully tested and validated during the pre-pilot phase with smart meter consumption data. As with CEVE, this data will subsequently be integrated into WIS4Households, and the platform is scheduled to become available to end users by April 2025.

4.1.1 Progress on pilot engagement

In this section we characterize the participants that will effectively participate in the pilot and compare with what we were planning.

CEVE, being a regional energy cooperative and local DSO in the North of Portugal, has proposed an EnC with 33 participants in their concession area near the building with the PV production unit. In fact, the PV unit has been installed in a pavilion that houses a Scout association and CEVE took the initiative to organize an information session to the residents nearby regarding the benefits of joining a renewable energy community with this site. In total, 33 participants subscribed, and this is the expected number of participants in the project.

Coopérnico, a national-wide energy cooperative, has targeted the participation of 100 end users in the project. A communication effort was undertaken with a selection of their clients, especially via e-mail, and at the pre-pilot phase, 85 have confirmed the participation in the project. However, the expected number of participants remains at 100.

4.1.2 Progress on infrastructure development and implementation

The table below describes the equipment that will be installed in the pilot’s demonstration activities and their status of development. This table refers to the development from the respective table related to the pilot infrastructure in D6.1.

Coopérnico pilot

Table 6 - Equipment characterization in the Portuguese pilot - Coopérnico.

Equipment						
Equipment	Expected number of units	Confirmed number of units	Expected number of new units	Confirmed number of new units	Status	Expected date
WIS-Connector	0	0	Up to 10	Y	Not installed yet	April 2025
Actuators for DR	0	0	Up to 10	N	Not installed yet	April 2025
PV systems with no batteries	n.a.	29	0	0	Installed by the end users	n.a.
EV					Installed by the end users	n.a.

CEVE pilot

Table 7 - Equipment characterization in the Portuguese pilot - CEVE.

Equipment						
Equipment	Expected number of units	Confirmed number of units	Expected number of new units	Confirmed number of new units	Status	Expected date
PV system	1	1	0	0	Not installed yet	April 2025
PV system	0	0	1	1	Not installed yet	April 2025
Battery system	0	0	2	2	Not installed yet	April 2025
Actuators for DR	0	0	Up to 10		Not installed yet	April 2025
WIS-Connector	0	0	Up to 10		Not installed yet	April 2025

4.1.3 Progress on data sources availability

The table below shows the development status of all the data sources that will be utilised for the pilot’s demonstration activities, which have been referenced in D6.1.

For Coopérnico pilot:

Table 8 – Data collection status for the Portuguese pilot – Coopérnico.

Partner Data Collection Template	
Coopérnico Customer Smart Meter	
Current implementation status	Testing
Expected availability date	January 2025
Smart meter data through HAN port with WIS-Connector	
Current implementation status	Under development
Expected implementation date	April 2025
Data from IoT actuators	
Current implementation status	Under development
Expected availability date	April 2025

For CEVE pilot:

Table 9 – Data collection status for the Portuguese pilot - CEVE.

Partner Data Collection Template	
CEVE data platform	
Current implementation status	Done
Expected availability date	Done
Data from IoT actuators	
Current implementation status	Under development
Expected implementation date	April 2025
Data from PV installations	
Current implementation status	Under development
Expected availability date	April 2025
Data from battery system	
Current implementation status	Under development
Expected availability date	April 2025

4.2 Impact analysis

4.2.1 Progress on the Key Performance Indicators

This section comments on any change in the data collection to effectively measure the selected KPIs and the quantification update as well. For example, the number of engaged citizens (through workshops, etc.).

At this pre-pilot stage, the baselines described in D6.1 did not change, besides the ones commented below.

Coopérnico pilot

Table 10 – Status of the key performance indexes for the Portuguese pilot - Coopérnico.

KPI	Name	Baseline	Comments	
Social	KPI1-SO1	N° of energy communities created and/or upgraded with active members	0	There will be no energy communities
	KPI1-SO2	N° of energy citizens engaged	0	85 have been engaged
	KPI1-SO3	Rate of engaged citizens that become activated (e.g. at the individual level or as energy community members)	0%	
	KPI2-SO1	% of energy bill reduction for energy community members	0%	
	KPI2-SO2	Energy efficiency (measured total cost savings of the system-level electricity distribution)	TBD	
	KPI2-SO3	% kWh supplied within the RECs / CECs	0	
	KPI3-SO1	Increased energy data sharing by active consumers	0	
	KPI4-SO1	% of consumers with sustainable (for more than 6 months) using DR automated solutions	0%	
	KPI5-SO1	Carbon emissions reduction (environmental benefit) measured at piloted local community levels of community engagement and the adoption of the new services	0%	
	KPI6-SO1	% of vulnerable households in the pilot energy communities with access to more affordable electricity	0	
Technological	KPI3-ET1	Share of new market roles designed, enabled and validated along the pilots	TBD	
	KPI3-ET2	New market participants as individual prosumers/consumers or through intermediaries (e.g. energy communities, aggregators)	0	

	KPI5-ET1	Economic benefit (measured as system-level cost reduction) of the adoption of community engagement and the adoption of the new services	0	
	KPI5-ET2	Share of increased aggregated flexibility the adoption of the new services	0%	

CEVE pilot

Table 11 – Status of the key performance indexes for the Portuguese pilot - CEVE.

	KPI	Name	Baseline	Comments
Social	KPI1-S01	N° of energy communities created and/or upgraded with active members	0	1 EnC is still under licensing process
	KPI1-S02	N° of energy citizens engaged	0	33 participants have been engaged
	KPI1-S04	Rate of engaged citizens that become activated (e.g. at the individual level or as energy community members)	0%	
	KPI2-S01	% of energy bill reduction for energy community members	0%	
	KPI2-S02	Energy efficiency (measured total cost savings of the system-level electricity distribution)	TBD	
	KPI2-S03	% kWh supplied within the RECs / CECs	0	Self-consumption of the existing PV unit.
	KPI3-S01	Increased energy data sharing by active consumers	0	
	KPI4-S01	% of consumers with sustainable (for more than 6 months) using DR automated solutions	0%	
	KPI5-S01	Carbon emissions reduction (environmental benefit) measured at piloted local community levels of community engagement and the adoption of the new services	0%	
	KPI6-S01	% of vulnerable households in the pilot energy communities with access to more affordable electricity	0	
Technological	KPI3-ET1	Share of new market roles designed, enabled and validated along the pilots	TBD	
	KPI3-ET2	New market participants as individual prosumers/consumers or	0	

		through intermediaries (e.g. energy communities, aggregators)		
	KPI _{5-ET1}	Economic benefit (measured as system-level cost reduction) of the adoption of community engagement and the adoption of the new services	0	
	KPI _{5-ET2}	Share of increased aggregated flexibility the adoption of the new services	0%	

4.2.2 Technology enablers evaluation in the pre-pilot phase

This section summarizes the different technology enablers (TEs) that will be deployed in this pilot, following what has been previously described in D2.1. In the case of this pilot, no changes have been identified, so the TEs to implement remain the ones described in the table below.

One remark, however, refers to the fact that WATT-IS and the Spanish pilot are discussing the possibility of integrating the non-intrusive load disaggregation from TE-13: WIS4Households, with the participants of the Spanish pilot through the data space.

Table 12 – TEs description in the Portuguese pilot.

TE-#	TE Description	Partner
TE-1	Interactive decision support tool for EnC planning	CARTIF, INESC TEC
TE-4	Energy Data Space compliant tools for sovereign data management, semantic interoperability and exploitation	ED, DST
TE-5	DLT/Blockchain/smart contracts multi-purpose marketplace for increased Trust & Sovereignty and for P2P tokenised assets sharing and compensation	DST
TE-6	Digital Twins for consumer activation	INESC TEC, DST
TE-7	Consumers clustering and segmentation tools	NTUA, UNIBAS
TE-8	FATEC - Flexibility Assessment tool for EnCs	INESC TEC
TE-12	OSTEC-Optimised Scheduling Tool for EnCs	INESC TEC
TE-13	AI-Powered Virtual Energy Manager (WIS4Households)	WATT-IS
TE-15	Blockchain-based hybrid coalition-based flexibility aggregation tool	DST, COMS
TE-16	P2P digital tools and platforms for consumer activation and social engagement	OurPower, BLUEPRINT

4.3 Pilot specific implementation plan

There has not been any significant change between the previously timeline at this point, so we keep the same Gantt chart as shown below.

5 Pilot 3 – Greece

5.1 Pilot status

The Greek pilot, ChalkiOn, focuses on establishing a community-centric energy system in the Chalki energy community. This initiative aims to optimize renewable energy utilization through advanced tools like demand response, and flexibility services. By integrating innovative technologies, ChalkiOn enhances energy autonomy, reduces costs, and promotes sustainable practices. The pilot has a goal to demonstrate scalable solutions for managing local energy resources, engaging community members as active participants in the energy transition, and showcasing a replicable model for other energy communities across Greece and the EU.

The ChalkiOn pilot has made significant strides despite initial challenges, including administrative delays and technical complexities. Several key installations have been completed, laying the groundwork for a functional energy community. Smart meters and electricity consumption meters have been deployed across participating households, small businesses and industrial sites, enabling precise energy monitoring and data collection. Additionally, an EV charger has been installed to promote sustainable mobility within the community. Interfaces for collecting and processing energy data have been established, creating a robust foundation for the integration of blockchain-based trading and demand response mechanisms.

Workshops and outreach activities are planned for the coming year to further educate community members, foster engagement, and refine operational practices. These workshops will focus on leveraging the installed technologies, optimizing energy usage, and facilitating peer-to-peer energy trading. Through these efforts, ChalkiOn aims to empower its members, demonstrate the feasibility of innovative energy solutions, and establish itself as a replicable model for community-driven energy transitions.

5.1.1 Progress on pilot engagement

In this section we characterize the participants that will effectively participate in the pilot and compare with what we were planning.

The participants have not changed in the pilot. ChalkiOn is the energy community that forms the basis of the pilot. PARITY has installed the EV charging station and monitors the related data via the EV Loader app and system. GEARS will provide services to the grid network operator to mitigate distribution grid congestion problems. NTUA develops algorithms for demand response based on data from the community. HAEE will coordinate the activities for consumers engagement and social acceptance assessment and conduct 1-2 workshop events on the island of Chalki. Various TEs are developed in conjunction with the pilot-specific activities and are overseen by other partners such as the Marketplace by DST.

5.1.2 Progress on infrastructure development and implementation

The table below describes the equipment that will be installed in the pilot’s demonstration activities and their status of development. This table refers to the development from the respective table related to the pilot infrastructure in D6.1.

Table 13 – Equipment characterization in the Greek pilot.

Equipment						
Equipment	Expected number of units	Confirmed number of units	Expected number of new units	Confirmed number of new units	Status	Expected date
PV station	1	1	Operational		Installed	
SCADA at PV station	0	1	Operational		Installed	
e-vehicles charging stations	4	5	Operational	1	Installed	
Energy meter at city hall	1	1	Operational	1	Installed	
Energy meter at desalination unit	1	1	Operational	1	Installed	
Energy meter at cafe	1	1	Operational	1	Installed	
Energy meter at residence	1	1	Operational	1	Installed	
Energy meter at hotel	1	1	Operational	1	Installed	
Energy meter at water tank pumping station	0	0	N/A		N/A	
Energy meter at submerged cable arriving point on the island	1	1	Operational	1	Installed	

Energy meter for EC members only	1	1	Operational			
V2G chargers	0	0	N/A		N/A anymore	
Energy meters on selected premises	5	5	Expected/Operational		Installed	

5.1.3 Progress on data sources availability

The table below shows the development status of all the data sources that will be utilised for the pilot's demonstration activities, which have been referenced in D6.1.

Table 14 – Data collection status for the Greek pilot.

Partner Data Collection Template	
iSolarCloud	
Current implementation status	Unavailable (API dispute)
Expected availability date	-
HEDNO	
Current implementation status	Offline, Excel format
Expected availability date	November 2024
Smart energy meter	
Current implementation status	Offline
Expected availability date	November 2024
HEDNO total	
Current implementation status	Offline, Excel format
Expected availability date	November 2024
EV Charging Station Consumption	
Current implementation status	Online (PARITY)
Expected availability date	August 2024

5.2 Impact analysis

5.2.1 Progress on the Key Performance Indicators

This section provides an update in the KPIs, revising the actual quantification of each KPI in the pre-pilot phase. Hence, should KPIs have started to be monitored, such as the number of engaged users or shared energy in the EnC, these values are then updated.

The KPIs stand as they were already declared in the previous update (D6.1) as there has not been any significant change in the development of the pilot case.

Table 15 – Status of the key performance indexes for the Greek pilot.

	KPI	Name	Baseline	Comments
Social	KPI1-SO1	N° of energy communities created and/or upgraded with active members	0	
	KPI1-SO2	N° of energy citizens engaged	0	
	KPI1-SO4	Rate of engaged citizens that become activated (e.g. at individual level or as energy community members)	0%	
	KPI2-SO1	% of energy bill reduction for energy community members	0%	
	KPI2-SO3	% kWh supplied within the RECs / CECs	N/A	The meter just got installed. The data are not yet available.
	KPI3-SO1	Increased energy data sharing by active consumers	0	
	KPI4-SO1	% of consumers with sustainable (for more than 6 months) using DR automated solutions	0	
	KPI5-SO1	Carbon emissions reduction (environmental benefit) measured at piloted local community levels of community engagement and the adoption of the new services	0	
Technological	KPI6-SO1	% of vulnerable households in the pilot energy communities with access to more affordable electricity	11	
	KPI3-ET1	Share of new market roles designed, enabled and validated along the pilots	N/A	TBD
	KPI3-ET2	New market participants as individual prosumers/consumers or through intermediaries (e.g. energy communities, aggregators)	178	
	KPI5-ET1	Economic benefit (measured as system-level cost reduction) of	0	

		the adoption of community engagement and the adoption of the new services		
	KPI5-ET2	Share of increased aggregated flexibility the adoption of the new services	0	

5.2.2 Technology enablers evaluation in the pre-pilot cycle

This section summarizes the different technology enablers (TEs) that will be deployed in this pilot, following what has been previously described in D2.1. In this pilot, no changes have been identified, and no TE has been demonstrated yet at this stage, so the TEs to implement remain the ones described in the table below.

Regarding TE-9, DL models for consumption forecasting have been developed using data from the Greek pilot. These forecasts, combined with PV production predictions from GEARS, have been integrated into a self-consumption optimization web application. Optimization algorithms have also been implemented and the application currently provides community-level self-consumption optimization recommendations.

Regarding TE-10, The smart meters related to comfort modelling have not yet been installed and the data re needed to continue the development of the models. Access to the Greek pilot energy smart meters was recently granted and the baseline daily consumption analysis has been performed. the closed-loop optimal control system is being integrated into the TE-9 web application to enable load adjustments

Table 16 - Status of the key performance indexes for the Greek pilot.

TE-#	TE Description	Partner
TE-1	Interactive decision support tool for EnC planning	CARTIF, INESC TEC
TE-4	Energy Data Space compliant tools for sovereign data management, semantic interoperability and exploitation	ED, DST
TE-5	DLT/Blockchain/smart contracts multi-purpose marketplace for increased Trust & Sovereignty and for P2P tokenised assets sharing and compensation	DST
TE-6	Digital Twins for consumer activation	INESC TEC, DST
TE-7	Consumers clustering and segmentation tools	NTUA, UNIBAS
TE-9	Self-consumption optimisation tool	NTUA, GEARS
TE-10	Closed-loop optimal load control and intelligent monitoring of electric appliances for residential users	NTUA, COMS
TE-11	V2G-based flexibility management platform for providing incentives to communities of EV drivers	PARITY

5.3 Pilot specific implementation plan

The plan stands as it was declared in the previous update.

6 Pilot 4 – Ireland

6.1 Pilot status

The Dingle Peninsula in Ireland is a rural community dealing with challenges in managing electricity due to network congestion and increasing electrification. This pilot program looks for new solutions in homes, farms, and transportation. Key activities include:

1. **Farming Flexibility:** Farmers will use renewable energy and flexible technologies through the Citizen Renewable Platform. This aims to save energy, cut costs, and reduce carbon emissions.
2. **Data-Driven Solution:** The program will analyse energy usage and production patterns. This will help improve self-sufficiency and community resilience. The Digital Active Platform will provide energy scheduling tips based on local weather forecasts.
3. **Community Engagement:** Residents will be encouraged to become "prosumers," meaning they will actively take part in the energy transition. The Citizen Renewable Platform will engage energy users to support renewable energy generation and flexible technology to enhance energy independence.

Overall, the pilot program aims to build a more flexible and resilient local energy system that benefits both the community and the environment.

6.1.1 Progress on pilot engagement

In this section we characterize the participants that will effectively participate in the pilot and compare with what we were planning.

The Irish pilot engagement strategy is structured around a thoughtful, staged approach designed to foster community participation in renewable energy initiatives. The first step in this process is to encourage new members to engage in a straightforward campaign aimed at activating their involvement. The initial campaign chosen is the energy broker initiative and was specifically conceived for its accessibility and zero cost, making it appealing to all community members. By focusing on this starter campaign, we aim to significantly boost the number of registered participants on our Citizen Renewable Platform (CRP).

The platform is central to the Irish Pilot activities and is designed to assist in lowering energy expenses through community-driven campaigns rather than relying solely on individual households. These initiatives encompass at different stages solar panel installations, LED upgrades, and energy tariff reviews. By collaborating as a community on collective energy campaigns, the aim is to effectively reduce costs and raise awareness. Participants on the online platform can securely store their information and express their preferences and interests in specific campaigns. The platform also facilitates the sharing of information about ongoing campaigns in Dingle, as well as the latest methods and technologies available to help decrease energy costs. Once registered, participants are under no obligation to commit to any campaigns.

Once we achieve a solid foundation of active participants through this introductory campaign onto the platform, we will leverage our successful experience to further increase participation. This will be accomplished by gathering positive feedback from 'champions' within the community and expanding our outreach efforts. The next phase will introduce additional campaigns, which may require a modest initial investment, namely the Phase 2 Solar PV campaign.

This is best understood as a journey of engagement envisioned as a transformative experience mediated through the Citizen Renewable Platform. Our pilot initiative will be propelled by the dedicated support of Dingle Hub, DC Six Technologies and four community champions, two from the Dairy Farmers Sustainable Energy Community (SEC) and two from the Tourism and Hospitality SEC. We believe these champions will create a positive ripple effect, encouraging further engagement from five additional champions within each SEC. These champions will participate in various activities, including demonstration events and sharing enthusiastic testimonials from early adopters, which we anticipate will substantially increase registrations for the CRP. At present, the Dairy Farmers SEC boasts a membership of 130 individuals, and the Tourism and Hospitality SEC similarly consists of 120 members. As we enter phase two of our initiative, we aim to secure CRP registrations from at least 10% of the total membership in both sectors, allowing more community members to benefit from our resources (i.e. 25 registrations by early 2025).

Energy literacy is a core concern in today's rapidly evolving landscape of energy technologies, billing structures, and policy changes. Thus, delivering precise and tailored information is critical to helping individuals navigate the plethora of energy options available to them, based on their unique goals and circumstances. Initial Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to track our progress in this area include community attendance at energy demonstration events and successfully launching the Tourism and Hospitality SEC Energy Masterplan. Monitoring the number of visits to our platform's landing pages and the overall registration figures will also be essential in gauging our success.

The Dingle Pilot has undertaken several vital activities, outlined chronologically below:

- January 2024 to June 2024: Implementation and completion of Phase 1 of Solar PV installations for both the Dairy Farmers SEC and the Tourism and Hospitality SEC.
- January 2024: Solar PV Open Day Demonstration specifically for Dairy Farmers SEC members, showcasing the benefits of solar energy.
- February 2024: The inaugural Data Sharing Workshop, where SEC community members engaged in discussions while beta testing the CRP Platform, allowing for real-time feedback and adjustments.
- April 2024: A follow-up Data Sharing Workshop to present recommendations on local data-sharing pathways to SEC members, focusing on three key areas: 1) Grid Flexibility and Demand Response, 2) Local Asset Optimization, and 3) Vehicle-to-Grid opportunities.
- May 2024: A Solar PV and CRP Open Day Demonstration aimed at the Tourism and Hospitality SEC, providing hands-on learning and engagement opportunities.
- June 2024: Conducting a Baseline Mobility Survey in Dingle to assess community transportation habits and preferences.
- June 2024: Launching an Electric Bus initiative designed to enhance sustainable transportation options within the community.
- July 2024: The exciting launch of the Citizen Renewable Platform Pilot Campaign, initially focusing on the 1.1 Energy Broker Campaign.
- October 2024: A significant launch event for the Tourism and Hospitality Masterplan, featuring an open registration session for community members interested in joining the CRP.

- November 2024: Initiating Phase 2 of the Solar CRP Campaign, expanding our efforts to engage more community members.

Looking ahead, we have a dynamic plan of events planned for 2025, including:

- February 2025: An interactive Energy Engagement Event to stimulate dialogue and knowledge sharing among community members.
- March 2025: The launch of the LED Upgrades CRP Campaign, focusing on energy-efficient lighting solutions.
- September 2025: The launch of the Heat Exchange CRP Campaign, aimed at providing innovative heating solutions.
- October 2025: Another engaging Energy Engagement Event designed to strengthen community involvement.
- December 2025: A follow-up Mobility Survey to evaluate the progress made since the baseline survey.
- January 2026: The commencement of larger-scale CRP campaigns, specifically focusing on 1.1 Community Led/Owned Energy Projects, empowering the community to take ownership of their energy futures.

6.1.2 Progress on infrastructure development and implementation

The table below describes the equipment that will be installed in the pilot’s demonstration activities and their status of development however may not reflect that of all the assets that will be considered in the pilot. This table refers to the development from the respective table related to the pilot infrastructure in D6.1.

Table 17 – Equipment characterization in the Irish pilot in Dingle.

Equipment						
Equipment	Expected number of units	Confirmed number of units	Expected number of new units	Confirmed number of new units	Status	Expected date
Agri Solar PV	50	-13	08 close to approval to install, 9 more planned for 2025	-13		Q2 2024
Agri Heat Exchangers	20	-	0	-		Q3 2023
Agri Wattrics Monitoring	10	10	10	10		Q4 2023
Agri battery	20	-	0	-		Q4 2025

Tourism & Hospitality Solar PV	25	-20	a further 20 in progress	-		Q2 2024
Tourism & Hospitality Heat exchangers	0	-	0	-		Q3 2025
Tourism & Hospitality Wattrics monitoring	16	16	0	16		Q4 2023
Tourism & Hospitality Battery	2	-	2	-		Q2 2024
Transport - Electric Vehicle Chargers	25	-	3	-	EV Charging infrastructure installed: 2 x 120kW electric bus chargers 7 x 100kW public EV chargers 10+ 22kW enterprise EV chargers 100+ 7kW domestic EV chargers	Q2 2024
Transport - e-Mobility hub	2	-	2	-		Q1 2025

6.1.3 Progress on data sources availability

The table below shows the development status of all the data sources that will be utilised for the pilot's demonstration activities, which have been referenced in D6.1.

Table 18 – Data collection status for the Irish pilot.

Partner Data Collection Template	
Wattrics Energy Monitoring	
Current implementation status	n/a
Expected availability date	n/a

ESB Innovation - Electrical model of distribution feeder	
Current implementation status	n/a
Expected availability date	n/a
120 Energy Management Plan Questionnaires	
Current implementation status	n/a
Expected availability date	n/a
Sustainable Mobility - traffic counters	
Current implementation status	n/a
Expected availability date	n/a
2 x 1000 Sustainable Mobility surveys	
Current implementation status	n/a
Expected availability date	n/a

The Dingle Peninsula, Co Kerry, Ireland, was chosen as the location for the project. The historical data sources used in the Dingle Electrification Project are:

- Smart Meters (AS230 block in Figure 4): ESB provided revenue metering data from 55 smart meters installed in the community for imported and exported active power in kilowatt-hours. The time range for the metering data is from 2019 to 2022; although from some smart meters the data is not available for the entire period.
- Solar PV Panels:
 - Data was collected from the solar photovoltaic (PV) installations at participating properties, focusing on energy generation and performance metrics over the trial period.
 - This data included the amount of electricity generated by the solar panels, the efficiency of the panels under different weather conditions, and the overall contribution of solar PV to the household's energy needs. Analysis of this could help in reducing dependency on the grid and contribute to energy sustainability.
- Air Source Heat Pump (ASHP):
 - Data from the ASHPs included detailed operational performance metrics, such as the amount of energy consumed by the heat pumps, their efficiency in different temperature conditions, and their overall impact on household energy consumption.
 - This data was crucial for assessing the effectiveness of ASHPs in providing heating and cooling, and their potential to reduce reliance on traditional fossil fuel-based heating systems.
- Residential Scale Battery Energy Storage System (BESS):
 - This data included the amount of energy stored and discharged by the batteries, the frequency of charge/discharge cycles, and the efficiency of the batteries in storing and releasing energy.

- The data was essential for evaluating the role of battery storage in enhancing energy flexibility and reliability, particularly in storing excess energy generated by solar PV systems for later use.
- EV Charge Point and Electric Vehicle (EV):
 - Data from EV charge points included detailed information on charging patterns, energy consumption, and usage frequency.
 - This data provided insights into how often the EVs were charged, the amount of energy consumed during each charging session, and the times of day when charging was most frequent. Furthermore, data from the EVs themselves included driving patterns, distances travelled, and energy use.
- DCSix have already provided metering data sets from 2 dairy farmers (consumption and solar PV generation) and energy data consumption from 1 pub with the breakdown consumption (beer garden, cold room, electric water heater, gas boiler and sockets).

Figure 1 illustrates the integration of the energy scheme used in the project. It highlights the various energy and data flows involved. This includes the use of smart meters and 55 SMs were analysed in the AS230 block function.

Figure 4: Energy scheme of the Irish pilot1.

6.2 Impact analysis

6.2.1 Progress on the Key Performance Indicators

This section provides an update in the KPIs, revising the actual quantification of each KPI in the pre-pilot phase. Hence, should KPIs have started to be monitored, such as the number of engaged users or shared energy in the EnC, these values are updated

Table 19 – Status of the key performance indexes for the Irish pilot.

	KPI	Name	Baseline	Comments
Social	KPI1-SO1	N° of energy communities created and/or upgraded with active members	0	2
	KPI1-SO2	N° of energy citizens engaged	0	135

¹ The dingle electrification project: customer flexibility trial. Ciaran Geaney, ICT Project Lead, The Dingle Electrification Project. July 2022

	KPI1-SO4	Rate of engaged citizens that become activated (e.g. at individual level or as energy community members)	0	29% (135 to 39 registering on platform)
	KPI2-SO1	% of energy bill reduction for energy community members	0	
	KPI2-SO2	Energy efficiency (measured total costs saving of the system-level electricity distribution)	0	
	KPI2-SO3	% kWh supplied within the RECs / CECs	TBD	
	KPI3-SO1	Increased energy data sharing by active consumers	0	
	KPI4-SO1	% of consumers with sustainable (for more than 6 months) using DR automated solutions		TBD
	KPI5-SO1	Carbon emissions reduction (environmental benefit) measured at piloted local community levels of community engagement and the adoption of the new services	0	
Technological	KPI3-ET1	Share of new market roles designed, enabled and validated along the pilots		TBD
	KPI3-ET2	New market participants as individual prosumers/consumers or through intermediaries (e.g. energy communities, aggregators)	0	39
	KPI4-ET1	N° of consumers engaged in automated DR (Ireland, Spain)	0	
	KPI5-ET1	Economic benefit (measured as system-level cost reduction) of the adoption of community engagement and the adoption of the new services	0	
	KPI5-ET2	Share of increased aggregated flexibility the adoption of the new services	0	
Scientific	KPI4-SC2	N° of CRP users engaged	0	# participating in one campaign: 15 % participating in second campaign: 2.5%

6.2.2 Technology enablers evaluation in the pre-pilot phase

This section summarizes the different technology enablers (TEs) that will be deployed in this pilot, following what has been previously described in D2.1. In the case of this pilot, no changes have been identified, so the TEs to implement remain the ones described in the table below.

Table 20 – TEs description in the Irish pilot.

TE-#	TE Description	Partner
TE-1	Interactive decision support tool for EnC planning	CARTIF, INESC TEC
TE-3	CRP social engagement management platform	DCsix, EPRI
TE-4	Energy Data Space compliant tools for sovereign data management, semantic interoperability and exploitation	ED, DST
TE-5	DLT/Blockchain/smart contracts multi-purpose marketplace for increased Trust & Sovereignty and for P2P tokenised assets sharing and compensation	DST
TE-6	Digital Twins for consumer activation	INESC TEC, DST
TE-7	Consumers clustering and segmentation tools	NTUA, UNIBAS
TE-15	Blockchain-based hybrid coalition-based flexibility aggregation tool	DST, COMS
TE-18	Privacy preserving tools for automated interoperable DR	EPRI, DCSix, MaREI, COMS

6.3 Pilot specific implementation plan

The plan stands as it was declared in the previous update, as there has been no significant changes.

Figure 5: Revised Gantt Chart for the implementation plan in the Irish pilot.

7 Pilot 5 – Hungary

7.1 Pilot status

The Hungarian pilot is an Early Adopter in the ENPOWER project, meaning that a selection of technologies developed in the other pilots will be replicated here. For context, Békéscsaba (BCS) is advancing decarbonization through its "Smart Microgrid Phase I-II" energy program, aiming to become Hungary's first city with full smart meter coverage to support local energy generation and consumption. A following development phase involves expanding energy assets and engaging municipality buildings, industries, and citizens in an energy community. While energy communities are new in Hungary, BCS plans to build one with support from Austria's OurPower and Hungary's ENASCO. OurPower will share expertise on citizen and industrial engagement, offer a P2P marketplace, and introduce its Nudging app, with BCS also replicating solutions from Chalki island.

This pilot, being an Early Adopter and so a replicator of the technologies presented in ENPOWER, has undertaken some developments in the planning for integration. However, these are still under discussion and further validations will be undertaken within the next months. Hence, this section does not present significant developments since D6.1 and the information being presented is considered as preliminary. Hence, a detailed planning and fine-tuning is taking place to assure a representative replication of the technologies in this pilot

7.1.1 Progress on pilot engagement

In this section we characterize the participants that will effectively participate in the pilot and compare with what we were planning.

7.1.2 Progress on infrastructure development and implementation

The table below describes the equipment that will be installed in the pilot's demonstration activities and their status of development. This table refers to the development from the respective table related to the pilot infrastructure in D6.1.

Table 21 – Equipment characterization in the Hungarian pilot.

Equipment						
Equipment	Expected number of units	Confirmed number of units	Expected number of new units	Confirmed number of new units	Status	Expected date
Smart Grid Phase I	1	0	1	0	TBD	TBD
Institutional prosumers	0	0	5	0	TBD	TBD
Webserver database	0	0	1	0	TBD	TBD
Smart meters	0	0	5	0	TBD	TBD

7.1.3 Progress on data sources availability

The table below shows the development status of all the data sources that will be utilised for the pilot’s demonstration activities, which have been referenced in D6.1.

Table 22 – Data collection status for the Hungarian pilot.

Partner Data Collection	
Planned web server for institutional members	
Current implementation status	Not yet implemented
Expected availability date	TBD
Planned web server for citizens	
Current implementation status	Not yet implemented
Expected availability date	TBD

7.2 Impact analysis

7.2.1 Progress on the Key Performance Indicators

This section provides an update in the KPIs, revising the actual quantification of each KPI in the pre-pilot phase. Similarly to the other sections of the pilot, these KPIs are still under discussion.

Table 23 – Status of the key performance indexes for the Hungarian pilot.

	KPI	Name	Baseline	Comments
Social	KPI1-SO1	N° of energy communities created and/or upgraded with active members	0	
	KPI1-SO2	N° of energy citizens engaged		TBD
	KPI1-SO4	Rate of engaged citizens that become activated (e.g. at individual level or as energy community members)		TBD
	KPI2-SO1	% of energy bill reduction for energy community members		TBD
	KPI2-SO2	Energy efficiency (measured total costs saving of the system-level electricity distribution)		TBD
	KPI2-SO3	% kWh supplied within the RECs / CECs		TBD
	KPI3-SO1	Increased energy data sharing by active consumers		TBD
	KPI5-SO1	Carbon emissions reduction (environmental benefit) measured at piloted local community levels of community engagement and the adoption of the new services		TBD

Technological	KPI3-ET1	Share of new market roles designed, enabled and validated along the pilots		TBD
	KPI3-ET2	New market participants as individual prosumers/consumers or through intermediaries (e.g. energy communities, aggregators)		TBD
	KPI5-ET1	Economic benefit (measured as system-level cost reduction) of the adoption of community engagement and the adoption of the new services		TBD
	KPI5-ET2	Share of increased aggregated flexibility the adoption of the new services		TBD

7.2.2 Technology enablers evaluation in the pre-pilot cycle

This section summarizes the different technology enablers (TEs) that will be deployed in this pilot, following what has been previously described in D2.1. In the case of this pilot, there are still relevant points that are being discussed between the technology providers and the pilot to determine the effective integration. We keep the provisional table presented in previous documents of the project.

Table 24 – TEs description in the Hungarian pilot.

TE-#	TE Description	Partner
TE-1	Interactive decision support tool for EnC planning	CARTIF, INESC TEC
TE-4	Energy Data Space compliant tools for sovereign data management, semantic interoperability and exploitation	ED, DST
TE-5	DLT/Blockchain/smart contracts multi-purpose marketplace for increased Trust & Sovereignty and for P2P tokenised assets sharing and compensation	DST
TE-6	Digital Twins for consumer activation	INESC TEC, DST
TE-7	Consumers clustering and segmentation tools	NTUA, UNIBAS
TE-9	Self-consumption optimisation tool	NTUA, GEARS
TE-10	Closed-loop optimal load control and intelligent monitoring of electric appliances for residential users	NTUA, COMS
TE-11	V2G-based flexibility management platform for providing incentives to communities of EV drivers	PARITY
TE-14	Nudging Apps for near real time closed loop consumers activation	OurPower, BLUEPRINT
TE-16	P2P digital tools and platforms for consumer activation and social engagement	OurPower, BLUEPRINT

7.3 Pilot specific implementation plan

The plan stands as it was declared in the previous update, as there has been no new confirmed information about the pilot implementation.

	Year 1												Year 2												Year 3																
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36					
Initiation																																									
Data and Information gathering																																									
Questionnaire circulation to the end users (T2.2)																																									
High level use cases definition																																									
Planning and design																																									
Business use cases definition																																									
Functional and non-functional requirements collection																																									
KPIs definition																																									
Baseline analysis																																									
Technology enablers implementation																																									
TE-1 Interactive decision support tool for energy community planning																																									
TE-4 Energy Data Space compliant tools																																									
TE-5 DLT/Blockchain/smart contracts multi-purpose marketplace																																									
TE-7 Consumers clustering and segmentation tools																																									
TE-9 Self-consumption optimisation tool																																									
TE-10 Load control and intelligent monitoring of electric appliances																																									
TE-11 V2G-based flexibility management platform																																									
TE-14 Nudging Apps for near real time closed loop consumers activation																																									
TE-16 2P digital tools and platforms for consumer activation / social engagement																																									
Evaluation of the demonstration activities																																									
First evaluation of the deployed TEs																																									
Second evaluation of the deployed TEs																																									
Third evaluation of the deployed TEs																																									
User satisfaction survey for end users																																									

Figure 6: Revised Gantt Chart for the implementation plan in the Hungarian pilot.

8 Pilot 6 – Spain

8.1 Pilot status

The Spanish pilot is also an Early Adopter in the ENPOWER project. For context, DSOs play a key role in the energy transition by leveraging flexibility resources like batteries and EV chargers. CUERVA, a small DSO, will develop a Green Community in Fornes, which is a fully digitalized village in Granada with more than 500 residents. The project involves installing PV plants at six public supply points (e.g., school, town hall) to share energy among more than 25 residential participants already enrolled. CUERVA and VERGY will engage prosumers through energy planning and gamification, replicating data-driven services tested in Portuguese and Irish pilots.

8.1.1 Progress on pilot engagement

In this section we characterize the participants that will effectively participate in the pilot and compare with what we were planning.

8.1.2 Progress on infrastructure development and implementation

The table below describes the equipment that will be installed in the pilot’s demonstration activities and their status of development. This table refers to the development from the respective table related to the pilot infrastructure in D6.1.

Table 25 – Equipment characterization in the Spanish pilot.

Equipment						
Equipment	Expected number of units	Confirmed number of units	Expected number of new units	Confirmed number of new units	Status	Expected date
PV system	1	1	1	1	Commissioned	January 2025
Electricity meters	-	-	-	-	In operation	-
EV charger	1	1	0	0	Not in operation yet	-
Wireless Sensors Network (WSN)	23	23	23	23	Not in operation yet	-
Centralized storage system	1	1	1	1	Not in operation yet	-
Smart meters	25	25	25	25	Not in operation yet	-

The defined EnC in the Spanish pilot has been identified, and the following table characterizes the main heating, cooling and air conditioning (HVAC) devices are described below, portraying the existing technology in the pilot.

Table 26: Identified heating, cooling and air conditioning (HVAC) devices.

Heating System	Cooling System	DHW System	Contracted PV Power in the community (kW)	Tariff
Chimney	Electric fans	Electric water heater	0.5	Free market
Chimney	Electric fans	Electric water heater	1	Free market
Chimney	Electric fans	Butane gas	0.5	PVPC electricity tariff
Chimney	Other	Electric water heater	1	PVPC electricity tariff
Chimney	Electric fans	Electric water heater	1	Free market
Chimney	Other	Butane gas	1	Free market
Electric radiators	Air conditioning	Gas	1	Free market
Chimney	Electric fans	Diesel oil	0.5	Free market
Chimney	Electric fans	Diesel oil	0.5	PVPC electricity tariff
Electric radiators	Other	Diesel oil	1	Free market
Other	Other	Diesel oil	1	Free market
Other	Other	Diesel oil	1	Free market
Chimney	Air conditioning	Other	0.5	PVPC electricity tariff
Chimney	Other	Electric water heater	1	Free market
Electric radiators	Other	Diesel oil	1	Free market
Electric radiators	Electric fans	Butane gas	0.5	Free market
Chimney	Electric fans	Butane gas	0.5	Free market
Electric radiators	Electric fans	Electric water heater	0.5	Free market
Heat pump	Air conditioning	Diesel oil	0.5	Free market
Chimney	Electric fans	Butane gas	1	Free market
Electric radiators	Electric fans	Electric water heater	1	PVPC electricity tariff
Other	Air conditioning	Gas	1	Free market
Chimney	Air conditioning	Diesel oil	0.5	Free market
Heat pump	Air conditioning	Butane gas	0.5	Free market
Chimney	Electric fans	Electric water heater	1	Free market

8.1.3 Progress on data sources availability

The table below shows the development status of all the data sources that will be utilised for the pilot's demonstration activities, which have been referenced in D6.1.

Table 27 – Data collection status for the Spanish pilot.

Partner Data Collection	
Type of heating, cooling and domestic hot water used by private users in the energy community	
Current implementation status	The characterization of the HVAC devices has been undertaken, and all devices are installed. However, individual monitoring is not available.
Expected availability date	The consumption data of the heating, cooling and domestic hot water systems will not be available for private users. However, other analyses can be performed, assessing the relation between total consumption and equipment characterization. Total consumption is available with a 1-hour resolution. In the public buildings, a total of 23 WSN are installed, from which data from the air conditioning systems will be available. Total consumption data is also available for the public end users with a 1-hour granularity.
Consumption of the users in the Community	
Current implementation status	Currently, hourly electricity consumption data for each user is available (both public and private). However, with the installation of the new smart meters, there will be near real-time granularity for each user.
Expected availability date	April 2025
PV energy consumed by each user	
Current implementation status	The PV system that will share the excess production with the EnC participants is installed and provides data with a 1-hour granularity.
Expected availability date	January 2025
General electrical data	
Current implementation status	Data available with a 1-hour resolution.
Expected	

availability date	
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8.2 Impact analysis

8.2.1 Progress on the Key Performance Indicators

This section provides an update in the KPIs, revising the actual quantification of each KPI in the pre-pilot phase. Hence, should KPIs have started to be monitored, such as the number of engaged users or shared energy in the EnC, these values are updated.

Table 28 – Status of the key performance indexes for the Spanish pilot.

	KPI	Name	Baseline	Comments
Social	KPI1-SO1	N° of energy communities created and/or upgraded with active members		n/a
	KPI1-SO2	N° of energy citizens engaged	25	n/a
	KPI1-SO4	Rate of engaged citizens that become activated (e.g. at individual level or as energy community members)		n/a
	KPI2-SO1	% of energy bill reduction for energy community members		n/a
	KPI2-SO2	Energy efficiency (measured total costs saving of the system-level electricity distribution)		n/a
	KPI2-SO3	% kWh supplied within the RECs / CECs		n/a
	KPI3-SO1	Increased energy data sharing by active consumers	0	
	KPI4-SO1	% of consumers with sustainable (for more than 6 months) using DR automated solutions	0	
	KPI5-SO1	Carbon emissions reduction (environmental benefit) measured at piloted local community levels of community engagement and the adoption of the new services		n/a
Technological	KPI3-ET1	Share of new market roles designed, enabled and validated along the pilots		n/a
	KPI3-ET2	New market participants as individual prosumers/consumers or through intermediaries (e.g. energy communities, aggregators)		n/a
	KPI4-ET1	N° of consumers engaged in automated DR (Ireland, Spain)	0	
	KPI5-ET1	Economic benefit (measured as system-level cost reduction) of		n/a

		the adoption of community engagement and the adoption of the new services		
	KPI5-ET2	Share of increased aggregated flexibility the adoption of the new services		n/a

8.2.2 Technology enablers evaluation in the pre-pilot cycle

This section summarizes the different technology enablers (TEs) that will be deployed in this pilot, following what has been previously described in D2.1. In the case of this pilot, discussions are still undergoing to determine whether these technologies will be included in the Spanish pilot, namely:

- TE-8: FATEC - Flexibility Assessment tool for EnCs (INESC TEC)
- TE-13: AI-Powered Virtual Energy Manager (WIS4Households) (WATT-IS)
- TE-12: OSTEC-Optimised Scheduling Tool for EnCs (INESC TEC)
- TE-17: P2P energy markets designs and algorithms (INESC TEC)

The remaining TEs to implement remain the ones described in the table below.

Table 29 – TEs description in the Spanish pilot.

TE-#	TE Description	Partner
TE-1	Interactive decision support tool for EnC planning	CARTIF, INESC TEC
TE-2	SITEC-Sizing tool for EnCs	INESC TEC
TE-3	CRP social engagement management platform	DCsix, EPRI
TE-4	Energy Data Space compliant tools for sovereign data management, semantic interoperability and exploitation	ED, DST
TE-5	DLT/Blockchain/smart contracts multi-purpose marketplace for increased Trust & Sovereignty and for P2P tokenised assets sharing and compensation	DST
TE-6	Digital Twins for consumer activation	INESC TEC, DST
TE-7	Consumers clustering and segmentation tools	NTUA, UNIBAS
TE-15	Blockchain-based hybrid coalition-based flexibility aggregation tool	DST, COMS
TE-18	Privacy preserving tools for automated interoperable DR	EPRI, DCsix, MaREI, COMS

8.3 Pilot specific implementation plan

	Year 1												Year 2												Year 3												
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	
Initiation																																					
Data and Information gathering																																					
Questionnaire circulation to the end users (T2.2)																																					
Workshops with communities (T3.1)																																					
High level use cases definition																																					
Planning and design																																					
Business use cases definition																																					
Functional and non-functional requirements collection																																					
KPIs definition																																					
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TE-15 Blockchain-based hybrid coalition-based flexibility aggregation tool																																					
TE-17 P2P energy markets designs and algorithms																																					
TE-18 Privacy preserving tools for automated interoperable DR																																					
Evaluation of the demonstration activities																																					
First evaluation of the deployed TEs																																					
Second evaluation of the deployed TEs																																					
Third evaluation of the deployed TEs																																					
User satisfaction survey for end users																																					

Figure 7: Revised Gantt Chart for the implementation plan in the Spanish pilot.

9 Conclusions

This document updates the developments undertaken by each pilot for their implementation, which is relevant to effectively manage the various layers and interconnections between technologies and pilots proposed in ENPOWER. For each pilot, a selection of development points is discussed and updated, beginning with the description of engagement initiatives and strategy, which reflect the importance given to the end user in accomplishing the project's goals. The KPIs are discussed. Then, any changes to the infrastructure are described and the data availability. Identifying any change or practical barrier in these points is significant to the successful implementation of the pilots. Furthermore, this document analyses the KPIs, outlining any updated quantification and the technology integration with the ENPOWER TEs, closing this document with an updated Gantt chart for each pilot. Regarding the definition of the use cases' activities in the Front Runners, since there were no major activities, these will be further monitored and reported in the next deliverable of WP6, D6.3. Also, in the case of the Early Adopters (Spanish and Hungarian pilots), there is still some information that needs further confirmation and discussion between partners to validate the technology integration and replication in those pilots. The information provided in this deliverable helps to effectively manage the development of ENPOWER.

10 Annex

The User Satisfaction Questionnaire is presented below.

User Satisfaction Questionnaire

Demographic Information (optional)

1. What is your role in the energy community?

- Consumer
- Producer
- Community Manager
- Technician
- Other (please specify)

2. How long have you been involved with the energy community?

Workshop Feedback

3. How satisfied were you with the overall workshop experience?

- Very Satisfied
- Satisfied
- Neutral
- Dissatisfied
- Very Dissatisfied

4. How would you rate the clarity of the presentations regarding the tools?

- Very Clear
- Clear
- Neutral
- Unclear
- Very Unclear

5. How well did the workshop meet your expectations?

- Exceeded Expectations
- Met Expectations
- Did Not Meet Expectations

6. How effective were the trainers in conveying the content?

- Very Effective
- Effective
- Neutral
- Ineffective
- Very Ineffective

Tool Specific Questions

7. Which tool(s)/ ENPOWER services did you find most useful for managing/ monitoring & controlling energy?

- (To provide a list of the tools/ ENPOWER services that were presented)

8. How confident do you feel in using the tools/ services introduced during the workshop?

- Very Confident
- Confident
- Neutral
- Unconfident
- Very Unconfident

9. Did the training provide you with the necessary skills to use the tools/ services effectively?

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

10. How likely are you to use the tools introduced in your daily activities?

- Very Likely
- Likely
- Neutral
- Unlikely
- Very Unlikely

Additional Feedback

11. What features do you think are missing from the tools presented?

12. What improvements would you suggest for future workshops?

13. Would you be interested in additional training or resources for using these tools?

- Yes
- No
- Maybe (please specify)

14. Any additional comments or suggestions?

Closing

15. Would you like to be contacted for follow-up discussions or additional surveys?

- Yes (please provide contact info)
- No

If the workshops include engagement activities

User Satisfaction Questionnaire (Adapted for Engagement Activities)

Demographic Information (optional)

1. What is your current involvement with the energy community?

- Current Member
- Prospective Member

- Not Involved

2. If you are a prospective member, what interests you most about joining the energy community?

- Sustainability
- Cost Savings
- Community Benefits
- Regionality
- Independence
- Other (please specify)

Workshop Feedback

3. How satisfied were you with the overall workshop experience?

- Very Satisfied
- Satisfied
- Neutral
- Dissatisfied
- Very Dissatisfied

4. How effective were the engagement activities in informing you about the energy community?

- Very Effective
- Effective
- Neutral
- Ineffective
- Very Ineffective

5. Did the engagement activities increase your interest in joining the energy community?

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree

- Strongly Disagree

6. How engaging did you find the activities designed for prospective members?

- Very Engaging
- Engaging
- Neutral
- Disengaging
- Very Disengaging

Tool Specific Questions

7. Which tools/ ENPOWER services introduced during the workshop do you find useful for managing/ monitoring & controlling energy, whether you're a current member or considering membership?

- (To provide a list of the tools/ ENPOWER services that were presented)

8. How confident do you feel in using the tools/services introduced during the workshop?

- Very Confident
- Confident
- Neutral
- Unconfident
- Very Unconfident

Additional Feedback

9. What features, or information would have made the engagement activities more appealing to you?

10. What additional resources or information would you need to consider joining the energy community?

11. How likely are you to explore membership in the energy community after attending this workshop?

- Very Likely
- Likely

- Neutral
- Unlikely
- Very Unlikely

12. What barriers do you see to joining the energy community?

13. Open-ended comments: Please share any thoughts or suggestions you have regarding the outreach and engagement activities.

Closing

14. Would you like to be contacted for follow-up discussions regarding membership in the energy community?

- Yes (please provide contact info)
- No

